

A STUDY TO ASSESS THE OCCUPATIONAL STRESS AMONG THE FRONTLINE NURSES WORKING IN GOVERNMENT MEDICAL COLLEGE HOSPITALS IN THE WESTERN DISTRICTS OF TAMIL NADU DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Dr. M. Punitha, Professor & Head

Department of Social Work

Hindusthan College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore

&

Anjali J Anil, PhD research scholar

Department of Social Work

Hindusthan College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore

ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic had posed a great challenge to the nursing speciality. Factors such as increased workload, long hours of work, need to wear the Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) during the duty hours, etc. imposed great deal of stress. Thus we performed a cross sectional study among the COVID-19 frontline nurses working in the Government medical college hospitals in the western districts of Tamil Nadu. Totally 360 responses were analysed. It was found that the stress was of moderate intensity in 15.3% of the respondents. The measures to overcome the stress among the front line workers in the future pandemics is also mentioned in this study.

INTRODUCTION

Nursing professionals are the backbone of the health care system. Their role is invaluable since they establish direct contact with patients. Their care and compassion plays an immense role for the efficient recovery of the patients. The COVID-19 pandemic had posed a great challenge to the nursing speciality. The increased workload, long hours of work, need to wear the Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) during the duty hours, need to be away from the family during the times of quarantine and isolation, inadequacy of medicines, PPEs, frequently changing COVID-19 guidelines and treatment protocols, stigmatization, need to face the dying patients and their relatives are some of the factors that had put immense pressure upon them.

Thus we intend to perform a cross sectional study among the COVID-19 frontline nurses working in the Government medical college hospitals in the western districts of Tamil Nadu. This study is intended to assess the occupational stress among the frontline nurses. This study will be a value addition since it is relevant to the recent pandemic. This study will be of great benefit to the

Government and private health care sectors to realize the degree of stress so that necessary measures shall be undertaken to prevent and resolve the stress among the frontline nurses.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Cui S et.al (2021) conducted a cross-sectional study to assess the psychological impact of COVID-19 on the registered nurses working in fever and emergency outpatient clinics who have been exposed to the COVID-19 epidemic for more than a month. The study was conducted in the hospitals in Jiangsu Province, China. The study included 481 participants out of which 453 participants responded to the questionnaire adequately. The online questionnaire which was self-administered was constructed using Self-Rating Anxiety Scale, Perceived Stress Scale-14 and Simplified Coping Style Questionnaire. In this study, excessive stress was seen among 32.23% of the respondents. While the participants who were more likely to respond to the stress positively accounted to 50.55%, those who were more likely to respond negatively accounts to 49.45%. Among the respondents, 62.03% had no symptoms of anxiety, mild anxiety was seen in 34%, moderate anxiety was seen in 3.53% and severe anxiety was seen in 0.44%. A significant observation in this study was that the Pearson correlation featured a positive correlation of the anxiety with stress score while the coping tendency correlated negatively with stress and anxiety.

Prasad K et.al (2021) conducted a study to assess the prevalence of stress and burnout among the healthcare workers in USA during COVID-19 pandemic. It was a nation-wide study. The study consisted of 20,947 healthcare workers from 42 organizations. A Stress Summary Score which consisted of items to assess stress, fear of exposure, workload and anxiety/depression was used as the tool of data collection in this study. It was observed in this study that the fear of exposure and transmission was seen among 61% of the participants. Anxiety/depression was seen among 38% respondents, overload of work was seen in 43% and burnout was seen in 49% of HCWs. The stress scores were higher among nursing assistants, medical assistants and social workers and inpatient workers. Fear of exposure was higher among the nursing aspirants.

Hong S et.al (2021) performed a study to assess the immediate psychological effects on the nurses working at 42 hospitals designated by Government for the care of COVID-19 infected individuals in China. The questionnaire comprised of socio-demographic variables, items related to perception and attitude towards COVID-19, items pertaining to experiences related to COVID-19 infection and job related stress assessment scale developed for health care workers during SARS outbreak (Tam et.al). The psychological assessment was done using items from Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9), Generalized Anxiety Disorder-7 (GAD-7) and Patient Health Questionnaire Somatic Symptom Severity Scale-15 (PHQ-15). Totally 4692 frontline nurses returned the complete and valid responses in this multi-center, cross-sectional study. It was observed that 442 nurses (9.4%) had depressive symptoms, 379 nurses (8.1%) had anxiety symptoms and 2005 nurses (42.7%) had somatic

symptoms. Suicidal ideation was seen among 306 nurses (6.5%). Thus it is evident from this study that the overall mental health of the frontline nurses was affected significantly during the outbreak of COVID-19.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Inclusion Criteria

All the frontline COVID care nurses working in the Government medical college hospitals in the Western Districts of Tamil Nadu, India who had to come into direct contact with suspected or confirmed COVID-19 infected patients were considered as the study participants. In the present study, only the staff nurses who are employed on permanent basis under Government of Tamil Nadu were included.

Exclusion Criteria

- 1) Staff nurses who were not in the frontline (who were not involved in COVID care)
- 2) Temporary and contractual staff nurses
- 3) Nurses who were not willing to participate in the study

Sampling

The sampling technique adopted in this study is convenience sampling. According to the estimation of sample size calculated using D Morgan and Krejcie sample size determination formula, 289 respondents constitute the significant sample size in the present study. Considering the significant sample size, the online questionnaire was sent to 390 frontline nurses. Among the 390 respondents, the questionnaires returned by 360 of them were found to be valid and were used for further data analysis.

Tools of data collection

A structured questionnaire was used to collect the demographic details. The researcher used Expanded Nursing Stress Scale (ENSS) which was adapted from French et al.2000 to assess the occupational stress among the nurses. It is a valid and reliable tool for assessment of occupational stress among nurses. The scale consisted of 57 items and the responses are to be rated in a 5 point Likert scale with '0' representing 'never exposed', '1' representing 'never stressful', '2' representing 'occasionally stressful', '3' representing 'frequently stressful', and '4' representing 'extremely stressful'. The questions were modified by asking the respondents to mention how stressful were the situations they encountered in their present occupational setting during the COVID-19 pandemic.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION**Table 1:** Depiction of the demographic variables and the ENSS cumulative score of the respondents

Variables	Distribution	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Age of the respondents	20yrs-30yrs	103	28.6
	31yrs-40yrs	205	56.9
	41yrs-50yrs	52	14.4
Gender	Female	360	100
Marital status	Unmarried	10	2.8
	Married & staying with spouse	304	84.4
	Married & staying away from spouse	37	10.3
	Divorced	9	2.5
Educational status	General nursing	86	23.9
	B.Sc Nursing	264	73.3
	M.Sc Nursing	10	2.8
Family	Joint family	169	46.9
	Nuclear	191	53.1
Health issues	Yes	21	5.8
	No	339	94.2
Type of health issue	Diabetic	8	2.2
	Hypertensive	13	3.6
Type of work place	ICU	68	18.9
	Ward	196	54.4
	Operation Room	60	16.7
	Out patient department	36	10.0
Total years of experience	Less than 5 years	64	17.8
	5 to 10 years	187	51.9
	10 to 20 years	86	23.9
	above 20 years	23	6.4
Infected with COVID 19	Yes	70	19.4
	No	290	80.6
Severity of COVID 19	Asymptomatic	281	78.1
	Mild	14	3.9
	Moderate	55	15.3
	Severe	10	2.8
Expanded nursing stress	84-150	88	24.4

scale – Cumulative score	51-83	262	72.8
	0-50	10	2.8

The questionnaire were returned and found to be completed by 360 respondents. Among the respondents, all were female. Majority of the front line nurses belong to 31 to 40 years age group (56.9%). The common educational qualification among the respondents was B.Sc nursing (73.3%). Health issues among the respondents were hypertension in 13 and diabetes in 8. Majority of the respondents were working in the wards (54.4%), followed by ICU (18.9%). Total years of experience was between 5 to 10 years in majority of the front line nurses (51.9%).

Among the front line nurses, 70 of them were infected with COVID 19 infection (19.4%). The infection was asymptomatic in 281 respondents (78.1%), mild intensity in 14 (3.9%), moderate intensity in 55 (15.3%) and severe intensity in 10 respondents (2.8%). The occupational stress was of moderate intensity in 24.4% of the respondents.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Certain measures to prevent the psychological distress among the frontline nurses and health care workers are proposed below:

1. Preparing the HCWs and training them to deal with potential pandemics
2. HCWs and their families must be regularly screened for the symptoms pertaining to anxiety, depression and stress
3. Providing stress management training programmes to the HCWs in groups, online format or self-help
4. To constitute a team to offer online counselling
5. Provide space for rest and refreshment/food for the nurses in the hospital
6. Offer training regarding coping strategies among the nurses
7. Establish good connection and communication with the people around the HCWs – both at work place and at home
8. Appreciating the HCWs for performing a crucial role in fighting the pandemic and motivating them to do their best with the available resources
9. If the HCWs are already being treated for mental health disorder, they need to continue with the treatment properly and they need to talk to the treating doctor if they experience new or worsening symptoms.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the profile of the front line nurses who were engaged in the management of COVID patients in western districts of Tamil Nadu were studied in detail. It was found that the stress was of moderate intensity in 15.3% of the respondents. The measures to overcome the stress among the front line workers in the future pandemics is also mentioned in this study.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Cui S, Jiang Y, Shi Q, Zhang L, Kong D, Qian M, Chu J (2021). Impact of COVID-19 on anxiety, stress, and coping styles in nurses in emergency departments and fever Clinics: A cross-sectional survey. *Risk management and healthcare policy*, 14, 585.
2. Prasad K, McLoughlin C, Stillman M, Poplau S, Goelz E, Taylor S, Nankivil N, Brown R, Linzer M, Cappelucci K, Barbouche M (2021). Prevalence and correlates of stress and burnout among US healthcare workers during the COVID-19 pandemic: A national cross-sectional survey study. *EClinicalMedicine*, 35, 100879.
3. Hong S, Ai M, Xu X, Wang W, Chen J, Zhang Q, Wang L, Kuang L (2021). Immediate psychological impact on nurses working at 42 government-designated hospitals during COVID-19 outbreak in China: A cross-sectional study. *Nursing outlook*, 69(1), 6-12.
4. Cui S, Jiang Y, Shi Q, Zhang L, Kong D, Qian M, Chu J (2021). Impact of COVID-19 on anxiety, stress, and coping styles in nurses in emergency departments and fever Clinics: A cross-sectional survey. *Risk management and healthcare policy*, 14, 585.
5. Galehdar N, Kamran A, Toulabi T, Heydari H (2020). Exploring nurses' experiences of psychological distress during care of patients with COVID-19: a qualitative study. *BMC psychiatry*, 20(1), 1-9.
6. Master AN, Su X, Zhang S, Guan W, Li J (2020). Psychological impact of COVID-19 outbreak on frontline nurses: A cross-sectional survey study. *Journal of clinical nursing*, 29(21-22), 4217-26.
7. Pal R, Yadav U (2020). COVID-19 pandemic in India: present scenario and a steep climb ahead. *Journal of Primary Care & Community Health*. 11:2150132720939402.
8. Said RM, El-Shafei DA (2020). Occupational stress, job satisfaction, and intent to leave: nurses working on front lines during COVID-19 pandemic in Zagazig City, Egypt. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(7), 8791-801.